

HIPPARCOS

Accuracy and Calibration of Main Grid

L Lindegren (1982 April 9)

Lund Observatory
Box 1107
S-22104, LUND, Sweden

Classification of Irregularities

Grid irregularities which are truly uncorrelated over more than a few slit periods (or a few arcsec) are of little concern as long as their amplitude is small compared to the photonstatistical phase errors for typical programme stars. They will merely cause a slight deterioration of the random errors but cannot introduce systematic effects.

Irregularities on a very large scale (correlated over large parts of the grid) are also relatively unimportant, since they can and must be eliminated in the course of the normal data analysis, viz. in the great-circle solutions. These are in practice inseparable from optical distortions caused by (possibly varying) structural changes and must therefore be recalibrated on a rather short time scale (few hours).

These two classes of irregularities, SSI (Small Scale Irregularities) and LSI (Large Scale Irregularities) have correlation lengths of the order of 1 and 1000 slit periods, respectively. Between them there is however a wide gap in which MSI (Medium Scale Irregularities) will occur, with correlation lengths of the order of 30 slits. For several reasons this class may be the most troublesome type of grid irregularity:

- On one hand, representation of MSI may require so many independent data points or parameters that we may not be fully confident in the feasibility of in-flight calibration.
- On the other hand, their number may not be sufficient to guarantee that the effects of MSI average out when the entire mission is considered, as can be assumed for the SSI. Thus, MSI may be a source of uncontrollable or hidden errors which are not revealed by normal checks and error analyses.
- Laboratory calibration of MSI may finally be impossible because of the high accuracy required (due to the small photonstatistical errors obtained when averaged over some 30 slits), and also because of the problem to obtain consistent measurements over centimetre distances in two coordinates.

Therefore it is reasonable to discuss accuracy and calibration requirements in terms of the three classes SSI, MSI, and LSI. The simpler division into only large-scale and small-scale distortions (the latter comprising SSI and MSI) used in the ITT is insufficient because of the large range of spatial frequencies involved and the peculiar nature of MSI. A finer division is however hardly motivated, unless they can be directly related to

the (as yet undefined) observing strategy, by means of spectral "windows" similar to those for attitude jitter.

Formal Definition of SSI, MSI, LSI

The following is an attempt to define the various classes in a more quantitative way, so that actual measurements on a real grid can hopefully be more or less directly related to requirements in terms of SSI, MSI, and LSI.

Imagine the ideal apparatus for measuring the HIPPARCOS main grid: a light spot of the same dimensions as the point spread function (about 0.5 by 1 arcsec in y and z) can be positioned with infinite accuracy on a rectangular coordinate system (y, z) fixed to the grid. For any given z -coordinate, a scan is made along the y axis and the varying intensity of the transmitted light recorded as a function of y (Fig. 1). From this curve, the middle point of each slit, y_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, I \approx 3000$, is determined e.g. as indicated in the figure. If such scans are repeated for a number of z -coordinates, z_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$, we obtain the distortion matrix

$$D(i, j) = \left[y_i(z_j) \right]_{is} - \left[y_i(z_j) \right]_{\text{should be}} \quad (1)$$

as the difference between actual slit positions and designed positions. The sampling interval in z , $z_{j+1} - z_j$, should be of the order of 1 arcsec, corresponding to the size of the analysing light spot. Thus $J \approx 3000$.

The total distortion (1) must now be split into three components,

$$D(i, j) = L(i, j) + M(i, j) + S(i, j) \quad (2)$$

corresponding to LSI, MSI, and SSI. This is done as follows.

Figure 1. Definition of slit centres y_j .

First the LSI are obtained as a third-order polynomial fitted by least squares to the distortion matrix:

$$L(i, j) = P_{00} + P_{10}i + P_{01}j + P_{20}i^2 + P_{11}ij + P_{02}j^2 + \\ + P_{30}i^3 + P_{21}i^2j + P_{12}ij^2 + P_{03}j^3 \quad (3)$$

Since this expression contains terms representing (for first order) also the effects of a translation, rotation, and tilt of the grid, and an error in the scale value, the subsequent definition of MSI and SSI will be independent of any (small) misalignment of the grid with respect to the measuring apparatus.

MSI are then obtained as a moving average of the residuals:

$$M(i, j) = \frac{1}{2n+1} \sum_{k=i-n}^{i+n} [D(k, j) - L(k, j)] \quad (4)$$

with $n = 15$ (say). Finally,

$$S(i, j) = D(i, j) - L(i, j) - M(i, j) \quad (5)$$

Acceptable Irregularities (No Calibration)

If there is the least doubt about the possibility of calibrating MSI and/or SSI, whether on ground or in orbit, one should require that the main mission objectives can be reached without any such calibration.

In practice this would put upper limits on acceptable MSI and SSI depending on the expected photonstatistical errors for typical stars. The latter are about 5 mas for 1 sec integration time on a $B = 9$, $B-V = 0.5$ star, corresponding to an average over some 135 slits.

If the SSI are allowed to contribute at most 10 % of the corresponding photonstatistical variance, the requirement on S is:

$$S_{\text{rms}} \leq 18 \text{ mas} = 0.13 \mu\text{m at } f = 1.55 \text{ m} \quad (7)$$

Due to the potentially more dangerous nature of the MSI, a somewhat stricter limit should be applied here. Taking 5 % of the photonstatistical variance, we get

$$M_{\text{rms}} \leq 2.4 \text{ mas} = 0.018 \mu\text{m at } f = 1.55 \text{ m} \quad (8)$$

Verification of (7) and (8)

Since the measuring apparatus mentioned above does not exist in real life, we must use indirect or partial methods in order to estimate S and M. At least the following three ways could be explored:

Manufacturing considerations. It may be that certain methods of manufacturing by their very nature, or by experience from their application to related problems, seem to preclude certain types of irregularities. This may be the case for the manufacturing of diffraction gratings either by holography or with ruling engines. In this particular case it may for instance be sufficient to verify (7) only.

Tests using integral phenomena. Examples are diffraction tests (using the grid as a diffraction grating and recording inter-order light scattering) and moiré techniques (whereby the grid is compared with itself or with another specimen). Such tests usually can only give certain statistical properties, since their sensitivity depends on some kind of integration over a large part of the grid, and only an upper limit, since other phenomena are usually also involved.

Very precise measurements over short pieces. E.g. a one-dimensional scan along y, a few millimetres long, will give, after subtraction of a moving average like (4), an upper limit on S_{rms} . This will be meaningful only if the measuring precision is better than about $0.1 \mu m$. If the nature of MSI is known (e.g. isotropy or stitching errors), it may be possible to obtain some information also on M_{rms} .

Calibration Requirements

If the grid can be shown to satisfy (7) and (8) then calibration should not be a strict requirement. It is of course still very desirable, but the benefit of it would in fact be a bonus not unlike that of dynamical smoothing.

If the grid will satisfy (7) but not (8), then calibration of MSI must be a requirement. The calibration should be accurate enough that the residual irregularities, after application of the corrections, will satisfy (7) and (8). This can probably only be done (to the full accuracy) in orbit, but I am not sure that a special calibration phase is required or even desirable. Another prerequisite for calibrating the MSI will probably be that there is good correlation of $M(i, j)$ over several arcsec also in the z coordinate, so that at most some 10^4 calibration points are required.

If the grid does not satisfy (7), then I think it must be rejected, since I very much doubt the possibility of calibrating SSI.

In-Orbit Calibration

The only tractable method I can think of to calibrate MSI is by a simple averaging of residuals. Thus great-circle solutions are made exactly as in the normal data reductions, whereby residuals are computed for elementary observations corresponding to stretches of perhaps 30 arcsec on the grid. These residuals are then sorted in bins (one bin per MSI mesh point, e.g. 30 by 30 arcsec). When every bin has received a sufficient number of observations, the residuals are averaged and the result (with opposite sign) is subsequently used as a correction to observations made on that particular point of the grid.

For this purpose I can see no strong reason for using any particular scanning mode different from the normal operational mode. On the contrary, it is probably better to have as "normal" conditions as possible in respect to revolving angle, spin rate, and change of spin axis direction.